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Behind the Chalkboard: The Hidden Struggles of Public School Teachers in the Philippines

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Being a public school teacher in the Philippines is a profession with significant challenges and difficulties. Despite the noble mission of educating the youth and shaping their future, public school teachers often face struggles that test their dedication and resolve.

One of the primary challenges is the workload. Public school teachers are tasked with teaching several subjects -often not their major of specialization, as well as handling large class sizes. This kind of situation makes it challenging to give individual attention to each student, hence affecting the quality of education.

Another significant struggle is the relatively low salary. Despite the increase over the past years, many teachers still find their wages insufficient to meet their basic needs and support their families. This forces them to seek additional sources of income or, worse, settle with bank loans to suffice their daily needs. Moreover, instead of using their income to pay their bills and buy their needs, they tend to spend it on the renovation of the classroom, purchasing instructional materials, cleaning materials in the school, and much more related to teaching. The low remuneration correlates or sometimes leads to a lack of motivation.

Despite these struggles, many teachers remain committed to their sworn profession. Their dedication to their students is commendable. However, teachers should not settle for these kinds of working conditions. The government's intervention is crucial in addressing these challenges and alleviating teachers' struggles. By providing resources, offering continuous professional development opportunities, and health maintenance subsidies, the government can significantly improve the quality of education in the Philippines.

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